

EFFECTIVE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CNT-EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effective electrical conductivity of an epoxy resin filled with the well-dispersed and randomly oriented carbon nanotubes (CNTs) was calculated by applying the micromechanical approach based on the model of the self-consistent composite cylinder assemblage, which includes three layers of CNT, interphase and epoxy matrix. The theoretical results predicted by this model for the CNT-epoxy nanocomposite filled with low volume content of CNTs (up to 5%) agreed well enough with the experimental data available (Figure). This validates application of such micromechanical approach to estimation of the effective conductivity of CNT-polymer nanocomposites. The parametric analysis carried out showed that effective electric conductivity of CNT-epoxy nanocomposite depends on longitudinal electric conductivity of CNTs, their volume content, and the interphase layer thickness, which is responsible on the so-called electron hopping conductive mechanism in the CNT-polymer nanocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since carbon nanotubes (CNTs) discovery in 1991 [1], they have rapidly become a subject of considerable scientific interest of the researchers and gave rise to a large number of publications devoted to their investigations and applications. This interest is based on a unique combination of their excellent mechanical, transport, and electromechanical properties, which were confirmed experimentally and theoretically [2, 3]. The nanoscale fillers such as CNTs or nanoparticles of silver and copper with at least one dimension less than 100 nm in size have significant benefits in comparison to microscale fillers owing to their high surface to mass ratio, higher aspect ratio and lightweight.

CNTs have opened up the great opportunities for development of advanced composite materials systems that have both tailored structural and functional properties. First of all, CNTs incorporated into polymer resins results in polymer composites with dramatically improved mechanical and transport properties with potential for use in a wide range of multifunctional and high performance applications. The electrically conductive composites can be produced with high electrical conductivity at very low volume content of CNTs (often below 1%). Electrically conductive CNT-polymer composites find engineering applications in the electronic, aerospace, biomedical, automotive, and etc. industries [2].

CNT-polymer composites are primarily composed of conductor-insulator heterogeneous material systems whose electrical conductivity can be tailored as desired. It should be noted that CNTs

significantly could increase the electrical conductivity of polymers without adversely affecting other physical and mechanical properties.

Owing to the change in electrical conductivity or resistivity under mechanical stress, CNT-polymer composites can be used as sensors and actuators in such potential applications as in-situ monitoring of stress distribution and active control of the composite structures [4, 5].

CNTs-based conductive polymer composites, applied as the resistance-type strain sensors provide a range of advantages over other types of strain sensors. The major advantage being that higher strain sensitivity can now be accessed. Flexible and stretchable strain sensors for use in novel applications such as large scale neuron sensor networks on engineering structures or working as human skins, as intelligent coatings or for bionic applications are now real possibilities.

Electrical strain sensors or strain gauges are usually categorized as resistance, capacitance, photoelectric or semiconductor strain sensors. The resistance type strains sensors are also referred to as the piezoresistive strain sensors.

CNTs are unique in the sense that strain induces a change in two key measurable properties (electrical resistance and vibrational frequency). Consequently, CNTs-based sensors have so far been developed for strain sensing at the macro-, micro- and nanoscale by taking advantage of piezoresistivity of individual or a network of CNTs, as well as CNTs-polymer composites, i.e. the change their electrical resistance under tensile or compressive strain [4].

To develop successfully the novel devices for such engineering applications, some of the major challenges, which should to be overcome, include in-depth understanding of structure-electrical conductivity relationships and response of the CNT-polymer composites under changing environmental conditions, as well as piezoresistivity of different types of CNT-polymer sensing devices [5].

The purpose of this research is analytical and experimental investigation of the electrical conductivity of the CNTs-epoxy nanocomposites. The micromechanical model applied for predicting the effective electrical conductivity of CNT-based nanocomposites is based on a self-consistent composite cylinders assemblage, accounting for nanoscale effects by incorporating an interphase layer outside the CNT. For validation this micromechanical model, the numerical results predicted are compared with the experimental data available

1 MICROMECHANICAL MODEL FOR EFFECTIVE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY ESTIMATION OF CNT COMPOSITES

Macroscale boundary value problem concerned with determination of the effective electrical conductivity of a polymer matrix comprised of randomly oriented, well-dispersed CNTs can be solved by methods of micromechanics of composites [6–8]. A multiscale modeling applied for this problem solution is shown schematically in Fig. 1. On the macroscale level, CNT-polymer nanocomposite is considered as a collection of the microscale representative volume elements (RVE) consisting of the randomly oriented nanoscale RVE. Nanoscale RVE is modeled as an assemblage of the concentric self-consistent cylinders assemblage consisting, of N layers of straight hollow carbon nanotube, surrounded interphase layer, and the outer layer ($i = N$) of polymer matrix. The interphase layer intended to capture the nanoscale effects of polymer structure perturbation and/or electron hopping.

As known, the steady state conservation of electrical charge equation at the macroscale level can be expressed as

$$\bar{J}_{i,i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where \bar{J}_i is the macroscale current density (or electric flux) vector and $\bar{J}_{i,i}$ denotes the divergence of the electric flux vector in terms of the Y_i coordinate system (see Fig. 1). It is assumed that \bar{J}_i obeys to the Ohms's law:

$$\bar{J}_i = \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^{\text{eff}} \bar{E}_j \quad (2)$$

where \bar{E}_j is the macroscale electrical field vector; $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\text{eff}}$ is a tensor of the effective electrical conductivity of nanocomposite. Since the electrical field vector \bar{E}_j can be expressed in terms of the electrical potential $\bar{\varphi}$ as

Figure 1: Schematic representation of self-consistent composite cylinders model application for randomly oriented, well-dispersed CNTs in polymer matrix.

$$\bar{E}_j = -\bar{\varphi}_{,j} \quad (3)$$

substitution Eq. (3) into Eqs. (2) and (1) gives that

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\text{eff}} \bar{\varphi}_{,ij} = 0 \quad (4)$$

By using the micromechanical approach, the problem of determination of the effective electrical conductivity of CNT-polymer nanocomposite $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\text{eff}}$ is solved in several stages.

1.1 EFFECTIVE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF NANOSCALE RVE

The first stage of the micromechanical approach is determination of tensor of the effective electrical conductivity $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\text{eff}}$ for the nanoscale RVE by using the method of concentric composite cylinders assemblage developed in [9] and generalized in [10]. This method is based on the set of homogeneous boundary conditions to both the multilayered composite cylinders assemblage for the nanoscale RVE and to an equivalent homogeneous effective nanofiber (Fig. 1). The permissible fields of electric potential of the nanoscale RVE ($\tilde{\varphi}^{(i)}$) and equivalent effective nanofiber ($\tilde{\varphi}^{(\text{eff})}$) should satisfy the conservation of charge equation under steady state conditions, expressed in the local coordinate system x_i , as well as to the corresponding boundary conditions. In the case considered, it is convenient to solve the appropriate boundary value problems in a local cylindrical coordinate system (r, z, θ) connected with the local Cartesian axes x_i ($x_1 = z$, $x_2 = r \cos \theta$, $x_3 = r \sin \theta$). Thus, we have the governing equation [6]

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{rr} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial r^2} + \tilde{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial r} \right) + \tilde{\sigma}_{zz} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_{rr}$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{zz}$ are the components of effective electrical conductivity of nanoscale RVE. Suggesting the transversal isotropy of the nanoscale RVE and nanofiber materials, we have that $\tilde{\sigma}_{rr} = \tilde{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} = \tilde{\sigma}_T$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_{zz} = \tilde{\sigma}_L$.

Equation (5) has two permissible solutions. One, $\tilde{\Phi}_L^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$, corresponds to uniform electrical conduction in the longitudinal direction L (i.e. axis z), but other, $\tilde{\Phi}_T^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$, in transverse direction T (i.e. axis r). The following solutions satisfy to the Eq. (5)

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\Phi}_L^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} &= A_1^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} z + A_2^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}, \\ \tilde{\Phi}_T^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} &= \left(A_1^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} r + A_2^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} \frac{1}{r} \right) \cos \theta, \text{ for } r_{i-1} \leq r \leq r_i,\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

where i ranges from 1 (the inner layer of CNT) to N (the outer layer of polymer matrix).

For determination of the unknown constants $A_1^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ and $A_2^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ in the solutions (5), we apply the following boundary conditions for electrical potential and electrical flux magnitudes

$$\tilde{\Phi}_L^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}(z = -L/2) = \tilde{\Phi}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\Phi}_L^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}(z = L/2) = \tilde{\Phi}_0 + \Delta\tilde{\Phi}, \quad (7)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\Phi}_T^{(N) \text{ or (eff)}}(r = r_N) &= \tilde{E}_0 r_N \cos \theta, \quad \tilde{J}_r^{(1)}(r = r_1) = 0, \\ \tilde{\Phi}_T^{(i)}(r = r_i) &= \tilde{\Phi}_T^{(i+1)}(r = r_{i+1}); \quad \tilde{J}_r^{(i)}(r = r_i) = \tilde{J}_r^{(i+1)}(r = r_{i+1}),\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

where L is length of CNT, r_1 and r_N are inner and outer radii of the composite cylinder assemblage correspondently, $\tilde{\Phi}_0$ and \tilde{E}_0 are electric field potential and intensity magnitudes.

The solutions (6) of boundary value problems with the constants $A_1^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ and $A_2^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ found in concordance with the boundary conditions (7) and (8) allow us determine the electric field energies of the nanoscale RVE, $W^{(\text{RVE})}$, and equivalent effective nanofiber, $W^{(\text{eff})}$

$$W^{(\text{RVE}) \text{ or (eff)}} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \tilde{J}_j^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} \tilde{E}_j^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}} dV \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{J}_j^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ and $\tilde{E}_j^{(i) \text{ or (eff)}}$ are the components of electrical flux and intensity in the local coordinate system x_i calculated by the Eqs. similar to (2) and (3).

This calculation leads to the following volume averaged magnitudes in the cases of longitudinal conductivity problem

$$W^{(\text{RVE})} = \frac{1}{2V} \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{V_i} \tilde{J}_z^{(i)} \tilde{E}_z^{(i)} dV = \frac{1}{2r_N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}^{(i)} \left(\frac{\Delta\tilde{\Phi}}{L} \right)^2 (r_i^2 - r_{i-1}^2), \quad (10)$$

$$W^{(\text{eff})} = \frac{1}{2V} \int_V \tilde{J}_z^{(\text{eff})} \tilde{E}_z^{(\text{eff})} dV = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\sigma}_L \left(\frac{\Delta\tilde{\Phi}}{L} \right)^2$$

and transversal conductivity problem

$$W^{(\text{eff})} = \frac{1}{2V} \int_V \left(\tilde{J}_r^{\text{eff}} \tilde{E}_r^{\text{eff}} + \tilde{J}_\theta^{\text{eff}} \tilde{E}_\theta^{\text{eff}} \right) dV = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\sigma}_T \tilde{E}_0^2, \quad (11)$$

$$W^{(\text{RVE})} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \int_{V_i} \left(\tilde{J}_r^{(i)} \tilde{E}_r^{(i)} + \tilde{J}_\theta^{(i)} \tilde{E}_\theta^{(i)} \right) dV \right) = \frac{1}{2r_N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}^{(i)} \left[\left(A_1^{(i)} \right)^2 (r_i^2 - r_{i-1}^2) + \left(A_2^{(i)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{r_i^2} - \frac{1}{r_{i-1}^2} \right) \right]$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}^{(i)}$ is an electrical conductivity of i -th layer of the nanoscale RVE.

Application of the equivalence principle for energies calculated for a heterogeneous and equivalent homogeneous media ($W^{(\text{RVE})} = W^{(\text{eff})}$) known as Hill-Mandel theorem, gives the

following formulas for determination of the longitudinal $\tilde{\sigma}_L$ and transverse $\tilde{\sigma}_T$ components of effective electrical conductivity of nanoscale RVE

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\sigma}_L &= \frac{1}{r_N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}^{(i)} (r_i^2 - r_{i-1}^2), \\ \tilde{\sigma}_T &= \frac{1}{r_N^2 E_0^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}^{(i)} \left[\left(A_1^{(i)} \right)^2 (r_i^2 - r_{i-1}^2) - \left(A_2^{(i)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{r_i^2} - \frac{1}{r_{i-1}^2} \right) \right]\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

Thus, the electrical tensor conductivity of the effective solid nanofiller in the local coordinate system x_i (see Fig. 1) is determined as

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(\text{local})} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_L & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{\sigma}_T & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tilde{\sigma}_T \end{bmatrix}\quad (13)$$

1.2 FLUX CONCENTRATION TENSOR APPROXIMATION

The procedure of determination of the effective properties of a multi-phase composite by means of any micromechanical approach requires the determination of appropriate concentration tensor components. According to Hill's conception [11], this tensor transforms the averaged quantity (e.g. stress, strain, electric flux, etc.) into a phase averaged quantity and characterizes a degree of interactions between the inclusions in the multi-phase composite. Some of the micromechanical methods developed (e.g., Mori-Tanaka method [12]) apply the so-called Eshelby concentration tensor. However, in the case of the multi-layered self-consistent composite cylinders method, the required components of electric flux concentration tensor $B_{jk}^{(\text{local})}$, expressed in the local coordinate system of the nanoscale RVE, can be calculated by using its immediate determination [13]

$$\langle \tilde{J}_j^{(N-1)} \rangle = B_{jk}^{(\text{local})} \langle \tilde{J}_j^{(N)} \rangle\quad (14)$$

where $\langle \tilde{J}_j^{(N)} \rangle$ refers to the electric flux averaged over the volume of the entire composite cylinders assemblage (i.e., over all N layers: $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$), while $\langle \tilde{J}_j^{(N-1)} \rangle$ refers to the volume average of the flux over just the CNT and interphase layers of the assemblage (i.e., over $N-1$ layers: $i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$). The electric flux components $\tilde{J}_j^{(i)}$ in (13) are the composite cylinder assemblage flux components in the nanoscale RVE expressed in Cartesian coordinates x_i using the following transformation

$$\tilde{J}_1^{(i)} = \tilde{J}_z^{(i)}, \quad \tilde{J}_2^{(i)} = \tilde{J}_r^{(i)} \cos \theta - \tilde{J}_\theta^{(i)} \sin \theta, \quad \tilde{J}_3^{(i)} = \tilde{J}_r^{(i)} \sin \theta + \tilde{J}_\theta^{(i)} \cos \theta\quad (15)$$

where $\tilde{J}_r^{(i)}$, $\tilde{J}_\theta^{(i)}$ and $\tilde{J}_z^{(i)}$ are calculated by using the solutions (5) derived for the above-described boundary value problems and the equations similar to (2) and (3), but written in the local coordinate system of nanoscale RVE.

Finally, the volume averaged electric fluxes (13) can expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\langle J_i^{(N-1)} \rangle &= \frac{1}{\pi r_{N-1}^2 L} \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{r_{j-1}}^{r_j} J_i^{(j)} r dr d\theta dz, \\ \langle J_i^{(N)} \rangle &= \frac{1}{\pi r_N^2 L} \sum_{j=1}^N \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{r_{j-1}}^{r_j} J_i^{(j)} r dr d\theta dz\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

1.3 EFFECTIVE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF NANOCOMPOSITE

One of the key assumptions accepted for the microscale RVE of the nanocomposite studied is that CNTs are well-dispersed and randomly oriented in the polymer matrix. This allows us consider the nanocomposite at microscale level as a two-phase microscale RVE consisting of similar solid equivalent nanofillers with random orientations in the polymer matrix. Orientation of the each nanofiller in the microscale RVE is determined by two Euler's angles ψ and φ (see Fig. 1). Considering that the microscale RVE is able to statically represent the overall effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite, we apply method of orientational averaging [14] for determination of the effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite. According to this method, tensor of the effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(\text{eff})}$ can be calculated as

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(\text{eff})} = \tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(m)} + \frac{v_f}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \left[\tilde{\sigma}_{ik}^{(\text{global})}(\varphi, \psi) - \tilde{\sigma}_{ik}^{(m)} \right] A_{kj}^{(\text{global})}(\varphi, \psi) \sin \varphi d\varphi d\psi \quad (17)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(m)}$ is tensor of electrical conductivity of polymer matrix ($\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = \tilde{\sigma}_m$, $i = j$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = 0$, $i \neq j$); $\tilde{\sigma}_{ik}^{(\text{global})}(\varphi, \psi)$ and $A_{kj}^{(\text{global})}(\varphi, \psi)$ are the electrical field conductivity and concentration tensors, respectively, expressed in the global coordinate system X_i ; v_f is volume content of CNTs un the nanoscale RVE.

To determine the electrical field conductivity and concentration tensors in the global coordinate system X_i we must perform the following transformation

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{(\text{global})} = Q_{ik}^T \tilde{\sigma}_{kl}^{(\text{local})} Q_{lk} \quad \text{and} \quad A_{ij}^{(\text{global})} = Q_{ik}^T A_{kl}^{(\text{local})} Q_{lk} \quad (18)$$

where the transformation matrix Q_{ij} from global X_i to local x_i coordinate system is determined as

$$Q_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \sin \varphi & \sin \psi \sin \varphi & \cos \varphi \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \varphi & 0 \\ -\cos \psi \cos \varphi & -\sin \psi \cos \varphi & \sin \varphi \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

and

$$A_{kl}^{(\text{local})} = \left[B_{kl}^{(\text{local})} \right]^{-1}. \quad (20)$$

Because of the accepted assumption of a random and uniform distribution of CNTs in the isotropic polymer matrix, the effective conductivity tensor of the CNT-polymer nanocomposite will be isotropic one.

Integration of (17) results in

$$\tilde{\sigma}_1^{(\text{eff})} = \tilde{\sigma}_m + \frac{v_f}{30} \left[\tilde{\sigma}_L \left(9A_{11}^{(\text{local})} + A_{22}^{(\text{local})} \right) + \tilde{\sigma}_T \left(A_{11}^{(\text{local})} + 9A_{22}^{(\text{local})} \right) - 5\tilde{\sigma}_m \left(A_{11}^{(\text{local})} - 2A_{22}^{(\text{local})} \right) \right] \quad (21)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_L$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_T$ are calculated by the formulas (11). Formulas for calculating the components of electric field concentration tensor $A_{ij}^{(\text{local})}$ are derived according to the description given in the section 1.2 (see (14)–(16)) by using the boundary value problem solutions obtained for longitudinal and transversal electrical conductivities of the nanoscale RVE ((5)–(7)). Because the derivation of these formulas is obvious due the above-given description, their specific forms are not presented here, for the sake of brevity.

2. EXPERIMENT STUDY

Nanocomposites used for the electrical conductivity experimental studying in LU PMI were made from the commercially available epoxy resins filled with different types of CNTs.

The first nanocomposite consists of DGEBA-based epoxy resin (L135i) with an amine hardener (H137i) (supplied by Momentive Specialty Chemicals, Stuttgart, Germany) and multi-wall carbon nanotubes Baytubes C150P (Bayer, Germany). This resin system is characterized by low viscosity (~250 mPa·s) and widely applied for fibre-reinforced composites produced by an infusion technology. According to the producer's data sheet [15], electrical conductivity of the Baytubes C150P is more than 10^6 S/m, length is 1-10 μm , inner and outer radii are 2 and 5-10 nm, respectively. The DGEBA/Baytubes C150P nanocomposite with different weight content of CNTs (0.05, 0.3, 0.5, and 1% wt.) was prepared by via a shear-mixing technique by using lab-scale three-roll-mill (Exakt 120E, Exakt GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany). After dispersing the CNTs required amounts in the epoxy resin, the amine hardener H137i was added in the ratio 100:30. These compositions were mixed for 10 min at angular speed 600 rpm, cast in a special mould, cured for 24 h at room temperature and post-cured at $T = 80$ °C for 15 h as recommended by the supplier.

The second nanocomposite consists of mono-component thermosetting epoxy resin RTM6 (HexFlow®) and multi-wall carbon nanotubes N7000 (Nanocyl S. A., Belgium), which were used without any purification treatment. This epoxy system was specially developed for the aerospace industries and applied in the resin transfer moulding technology. This epoxy resin is characterized by high glass transition temperature (200°C) and low density (~50 mPa·s) with the temperature range of 100-120 °C. According to the producer's data sheet [16], carbon nanotubes N7000 have the following average characteristics: length of 10 μm , diameter of 9.5 nm, and aspect ratio of 500. An exclusive catalytic carbon vapor deposition process provides for CNTs NC7000 the highest electrically conductive available today (up to 10^7 S/m). Moreover, CNTs NC7000 have one of the most perfect chemical surfaces enabling high efficiency in the matrix in which they are embedded. This nanocomposite (RTM6/NC7000) was prepared also with different weight content of CNTs (0.03, 0.05, 0.15, and 0.30% wt.) by using a high-performance disperser (T25 digital ULTRA-TURRAX, Werke Staufen/Germany). CNTs NC7000 were mixed in the epoxy resin of 60°C during 70 min at nominal disperser speed of 6000 rpm, which produces extremely a strong shear and thrust forces and provides as a result optimum mixing of the nanocomposite components. The prepared mixtures were cast in an aluminum mould (210×210×3 mm), which initially was treated with release agent Frekote (Loctite Frewax), degassed in a vacuum oven *Memert* at 90 C for 40 min, and then cured 75 min at 160 C followed by 120 min at 180 C. All nanocomposite specimens were post-cured 120 min at 70 C.

The plates of the DGEBA/Baytubes C150P and RTM6/NC7000 nanocomposites fabricated were cut on the flat specimens (110×10×2.2 mm). For electrical conductivity measurement, the electrodes made of a silver conductive paste were formed on the specimen surfaces. The specimens' electric resistance R was measured by the two-probe method, based on Ohm's law. The averaged values of specific resistance $\check{\rho}$ of the nanocomposites calculated from at least three tested specimens are presented in the Table.

v_f , % wt.	$\check{\rho}$, K Ω ·m	
	RTM6/NC7000	DGEBA/Baytubes C150P
0.03	150	–
0.05	1.7	12.5
0.15	0.03	–
0.30	0.008	1.0
0.50	–	0.3
1.00	–	0.1

Table: Values of specific resistance of nanocomposites at different weight content of CNTs.

3. CALCULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The micromechanical approach described was applied for calculation of the effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite containing the CNTs well-dispersed and randomly oriented in an epoxy resin. The nanoscale RVE for this nanocomposite considered consists of three layers: CNT ($i = 1$), interphase ($i = 2$) and matrix ($i = 3$) (see Fig. 1). The micromechanical model includes the following parameters: outer radius (r_1) and thickness ($t_1 = r_1 - r_0$) of CNT, thickness of interphase ($t_2 = r_2 - r_1$) and matrix ($t_3 = r_3 - r_2$) layers, electrical conductivity of the layers $\tilde{\sigma}_1$, $\tilde{\sigma}_2$, $\tilde{\sigma}_3$, and volume content of CNTs in the nanocomposite v_f . The outer radius r_3 of the matrix layer equaled to the outer radius of the composite cylinder assemblage r_{out} is determined $r_3 = r_1 / \sqrt{v_f}$.

The results of numerical modelling will undoubtedly depend on the values of the micromechanical model parameters. Experimental determination of some parameters of the micromechanical model (e.g. thickness and conductivity of the interfacial layer, thickness and inner diameter of CNTs) is very difficult. There is uncertainty about the ranges of their changes in the scientific papers published. Therefore, the initial values were taken as in [7]: $\tilde{\sigma}_2 = \tilde{\sigma}_{int} = 10^{-6}$ S/m, $r_1 = 1.0$ nm, $t_1 = 0.34$ nm, $t_2 = 2.5$ nm; $\tilde{\sigma}_3 = \tilde{\sigma}_m = 9 \cdot 10^{-9}$ S/m as in [8] for DGEBA-based epoxy resin.

The reliability of the effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites calculated by means of the micromechanical approach was initially verified by comparison with the experimental data available. For this purpose, numerical calculations are carried out with different values of the electrical conductivity of CNTs ($\tilde{\sigma}_1 = \tilde{\sigma}_{CNT} = 10^7$ S/m (for NC7000) [16], $1.85 \cdot 10^5$ S/m [17], $5 \cdot 10^4$ S/m [18], and 10^4 S/m [19]). These results are presented by the curves 1–4, respectively, in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Effective electrical conductivity of CNT-epoxy nanocomposite $\tilde{\sigma}_1^{eff}$ via volume content of CNTs v_f . Prediction (curves 1–4) and experimental data: \square [17]; \circ [18], \diamond [19] and \blacktriangle , \bullet [LU PMI].

It is seen that the theoretical prognoses are fairly good agreed with the experimental data given in [18–20], as well as for the RTM6/NC7000 nanocomposite (see Table). However, the calculated values of effective electrical conductivity for the DGEBA/Baytubes C150P nanocomposite were significantly greater than experimental ones (see Table). It seems, that the main reason is calculation with the overestimated value $\tilde{\sigma}_1 = 10^6$ S/m chosen according with the producer's data sheet [15]. The results of

experimental investigation of electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites filled with different multi-wall CNTs [20, 21] confirm this assumption. The measured values of electrical conductivity for the nanocomposites filled with Baytubes C150P were the lowest ones.

Good enough agreement between the analytical and experimental results validates the application of the micromechanical model applied for estimation of the effective electrical conductivity of the polymer resins filled with well-dispersed and randomly oriented CNTs.

The RTM6/NC7000 nanocomposite has the lowest electrical percolation threshold, while the DGEBA/Baytubes C150P nanocomposite requires the highest amount of nanotubes to achieve percolation (see Fig. 2). The same results were obtained in [20, 21] for the nanocomposites filled with different carbon nanotubes. Such different behavior of the DGEBA/Baytubes C150 and RTM6/NC7000 nanocomposites is explained by a much higher electrical conductivity of NC7000 nanotubes, greater length and aspect ratio in comparison with Baytubes C150P [20]. Moreover, the paper [20] concludes that the infiltration process of polymer resin chains into Baytubes C150P nanotubes is more difficult, which leads to a lower level of dispersion, and as a result requires their higher amount to reach the electrical percolation threshold.

The experimental values of the electrical percolation threshold, lower than those calculated according to geometrical continuum percolation theory [20], can be explained by such nanoscale effects as hopping [6, 22–24] or tunneling [24–27] for electron transport, which do not require direct contact between the carbon nanotubes. However, the true mechanism of providing such a low percolation threshold is debatable until now. There are different opinions that a low experimental electrical percolation threshold of the nanocomposites may be associated with both the electron hopping and the formation of conductive networks within the polymer matrix. But, the fact of low electrical conductivity percolation threshold of CNT-polymer nanocomposites characterizes their extreme sensitivity and paves the real way for the development of advanced sensors [5, 27].

The effects of material and geometry parameters (electrical conductivity and thickness of CNTs, thickness of interphase layer) of the micromechanical model on the effective electrical conductivity of CNT-epoxy composite were studied by means of the parametric analysis.

Depending on the manufacturing techniques, the electrical conductivity of CNTs varies over a wide range of values ($\approx 10^2 \div 10^7$ S/m) [8]. As seen from the numerical results presented in Fig. 3, an influence of the electrical conductivity of CNTs can be very significant. Naturally, the higher electrical conductivity of CNTs, $\tilde{\sigma}_1$, the higher the effective electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite $\tilde{\sigma}_1^{(eff)}$.

Figure 3: Effective electrical conductivity of CNT-epoxy nanocomposite $\tilde{\sigma}_1^{(eff)}$ via volume content of CNTs v_f at various values of the CNTs electrical conductivity $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ (numbers 1–5 at the curves).

The interphase layer with an enhanced electrical conductivity, which surrounds the CNT in the nanoscale RVE, is introduced in the micromechanical model (see Fig. 1) to consider an electron hopping effects in the polymer nanocomposites [6]. There are various estimations about the electron hopping distance in the literature. Its range is determined between 5 and 30 nm in [6]. The results of calculation (at $\bar{\sigma}_1 = 10^4$ S/m,) presented in Fig. 4 confirm that the effective electrical conductivity of nanocomposite is influenced significantly on the interphase layer thickness. Recall that the electrical conductivity of the interfacial layer $\bar{\sigma}_{int}$ in the micromechanical approach considered is adopted by a constant value and chosen equal to $\bar{\sigma}_2 = 10^{-6}$ S/m.

Figure 4: Effective electrical conductivity of CNT-epoxy nanocomposite $\bar{\sigma}_1^{eff}$ via volume content of CNTs v_f at various values of the thickness of interphase layer (numbers 1–5 at the curves).

The parametric analysis results (see Figs. 3 and 4) demonstrate that electrical percolation threshold of CNT-epoxy nanocomposite decreases with increasing both the CNT electrical conductivity and interphase layer thickness.

It should be noted that the more complex nanoscale CNT–polymer interface was considered in [23], where it was modeled through the coupled electromechanical cohesive zones within a finite element based on computational micromechanics framework. Such modeling allowed the authors to consider such effects as interfacial separation and damage.

In [8], it was stated that the CNT length has a strong effect on the electrical percolation rate of the nanocomposite. This allowed making a conclusion that overall electrical conductivity of the CNT-polymer nanocomposites can be improved by increasing of the CNT aspect ratio.

The CNT-polymer composites can be used for a variety of aerospace and naval applications including “electrostatic dissipation ($< 10^4$ S/m), electrostatic painting (10^{-4} – 10^1 S/m), electromagnetic interference shielding ($> 10^1$ S/m)” [28]. Therefore, this research will be extended on the studying of the piezoresistivity in the FRP composites with a modified matrix filled with carbon nanotubes.

CONCLUSIONS

The micromechanical model based on the self-consistent composite cylinder assemblage was applied to calculate of the effective electrical conductivity of the epoxy resin filled with the well-dispersed and randomly oriented carbon nanotubes. The results predicted by use this model agree well with the experimental data available, which validates of micromechanical approach application to estimation of effective electrical conductivity on CNT-polymer nanocomposites. The results of parametric analysis showed that the effective electric conductivity of CNT-polymer nanocomposite can be increased by increasing of the electric conductivity of CNTs, as well as the thickness of the interphase layer, which is responsible on the so-called electron hopping mechanism in the CNT-

polymer nanocomposites. The low percolation threshold can be also decreased by increasing the values of these parameters of the micromechanical model.

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